

Report

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Experiment Design for Data Science

Workflow analysis of data science code in public GitHub repositories

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Contents

1	Strategies	1
1.1	Multi Label Classification	1
1.2	Single Label Classification	2
1.3	Number Of Labels	2
1.4	Transition Matrix Analysis	2
2	Key Findings	2
2.1	Multi Label Classification	2
2.2	Single Label Classification	3
2.3	Number Of Labels	3
2.4	Transition Matrix Analysis	4
3	Difficulties	4
3.1	Multi Label Classification	4
3.2	Single Label Classification	4
3.3	Number Of Labels	5
3.4	Transition Matrix Analysis	5
4	Conclusion About The Experimental Design	5
	Appendix A	6
	Appendix B	6

1 Strategies

1.1 Multi Label Classification

In order to expand the DASWOW data set, supervised calssifications models were used. The objective is to predict the data science step from the lines of code and additional software information. The multilabelling algorithms used were the following:

- Random Forest Classifier
- Decision Tree Classifier
- Gradient Boosting Classifier
- Linear SVC
- Support Vector Machine
- Logistic Regression

To replicate the results of the paper, we used the same preprocessing on the same data and trained the models and searched for the best hyperparameters using Grid search with cross-validation. Within the preprocessing we tried different parameters for the vectorization of the text features e.g. N-gram range or maximum document frequency. When training the models, we tried out various random states.

1.2 Single Label Classification

For the single label classification we use the same preprocessing on the data, train the model and search for the best hyperparameters. The algorithms are the same as in **Multi Label Classification**. Contrary to the multi label classification, we only predict on one label at time. To replicate the results we tried several random states to check whether we observe the same results.

1.3 Number Of Labels

The analysis focuses on understanding the occurrences of data science steps in notebooks. The frequency distribution of labels of data science steps in each code cell was computed, as well as the distribution of labels in notebooks with and without the modeling step. The analysis provides insights into the composition and frequency of data science steps, for further understanding the progression of steps and their interrelationships is emphasized to support data scientists in their analyses. This research strategy involves a thorough annotation process, addressing challenges, improving instructions, and employing external annotators. The subsequent analysis provides more insights into the characteristics of data science workflows represented in the annotated notebooks, that can support designing tools that assist data scientists while creating and managing their data science process.

1.4 Transition Matrix Analysis

The transition probability between the different states is computed with the Markov Chain Model, where the different types of data science steps are represented as states. For the model the first order Markov chain model is used, meaning that each subsequent state only depends on the immediately preceding one. For code cells that have multiple labels, the order of their appearance is not taken into account, therefore, each edge is assigned the same probability.

For a better visual representation a Sankey Flow Diagram of the transition matrix is additionally generated.

2 Key Findings

2.1 Multi Label Classification

Overall, the results of the multi-classifier were replicated. The deviations we obtained are extremely slight. Also, by changing the parameters, the deviations are still very

small. The following table shows an example of how small the deviations are.

Metric	Paper	Our Results
F1 Score (RF)	0.711	0.703
Subset Accuracy (RF)	0.587	0.589
Precision (helper_functions)	0.92	0.91

Table 1: Comparison of Results for Multi Label Classification

2.2 Single Label Classification

It can be observed that the single-label classification can be replicated. The results only slightly deviates from the papers outcome. While the outcome of the accuracy and F1-score metric are almost identical with the exception of the F1-score for gradient boosting, the other metrics like classification report for the random forest classifier or the confusion matrix show small differences but highlight in general the same values as in the paper. When we choose another random seed, for example 1000, we notice that the accuracy and the F1-score are slightly decreased meaning that the random seed of 500 set in the original model is favourable for the performance measures.

Interestingly, they state in the paper that Gradient Boosting is the one algorithm with the second highest accuracy with 0.693 for the feature set `all-features` which is not true. When we check the paper, we can observe that the accuracy for `all-features` is below this value with 0.638. When checking the accuracy of the `code-stat` set for Gradient Boosting, it can be seen that this accuracy matches the description in the paper.

Metric	Paper	Our Results	Our Results Random Seed 1000
F1 Score (RF)	0.703	0.703	0.698
Subset Accuracy (RF)	0.711	0.711	0.707
Precision (helper_functions)	0.82	0.83	0.82

Table 2: Comparison of Results for Single Label Classification

2.3 Number Of Labels

The dataset encompasses a diverse array of steps, including data exploration, data pre-processing, modeling, helper functions, load data, evaluation, prediction, result visualization, comment-only, and save results, offering insights into the distribution of labels across various data science steps. The breakdown of these reveals their respective percentages in the dataset, showing the occurrence of each data science step. The distribution of the number of labels assigned to code cells shows that, the majority of cells are associated with a single primary label, with data exploration and data preprocessing being the most frequent steps. Additionally, the distribution of primary labels provides

a perspective on the prevalence of specific tasks, with the modeling step being more prominent. The analysis extends to assessing the correlation between the distribution of true values and predicted values using Kendall's correlation coefficient. The calculated coefficient, while indicating a moderate positive correlation, comes short of statistical significance ($p=0.136$). This suggests that there may be some alignment between the true and predicted label distributions, but we cannot draw definitive conclusions. Furthermore, the code explores the distribution of single labels, emphasizing steps alone. This examination shows the occurrence of data science steps, offering more insights into the dataset. Notable observations include the prominence of data exploration, data preprocessing, and modeling as single steps.

2.4 Transition Matrix Analysis

Through the transition matrix and the Sankey diagram generated one can conclude, that the data science workflow is an iterative process. Especially for the steps `data_preprocessing` and `data_exploration` as well as the modelling, evaluation and prediction unique iterative patterns were found.

3 Difficulties

In Table 4 the possible and encountered difficulties are listed.

3.1 Multi Label Classification

In total, the results were easy to reproduce and only a few changes to the code were necessary.

3.2 Single Label Classification

The results for the single label classification were easy to obtain and only a few adjustments to the code had to be made. However, there is the issue with the lack of clear guidance within the code itself. The paper states that multiple performance evaluations are done with multiple feature sets. However, there is no indication how to derive five of the six feature sets in the code, so it is hard to derive these. There is the possibility to change the code according to the paper where you add to the variable `features` not only text, which represents the lines of code in DASWOW but also additionally `comment`. Due to this change the number of feature vector increases from 48.485 to 56.123. Furthermore, this also changes the performance outcome which can be seen in Appendix A. The differences between the results of the study and ours are depending on the model more or less noticeable.

3.3 Number Of Labels

In total, the results were easy to reproduce and only a few changes to the code were necessary.

3.4 Transition Matrix Analysis

Generally, there were no problems in the `transition_matrix_analysis.ipynb`. However, for the Sankey visualisation it was not possible to save the image as an eps file. This problem was solved by saving it as a pdf file.

In the paper there are two different transition matrices depicted, however, in the provided code only one is generated. Therefore, only the transition probabilities for the predicted set of labels could be reproduced, but not the ones from the original data set.

4 Conclusion About The Experimental Design

Other studies additionally conducted interviews and surveys with data scientists to get a better insight in their workflow. This could have been a nice addition.

Furthermore, the manual selection of the jupyter notebooks could be biased. One could have generated a database with fitting notebooks and randomly choose the notebooks to avoid subconscious bias.

The paper assumes that the project size has no influence on the approach of data scientists. This assumption could lead to false results. One should either try to analyse notebooks of equal sizes or conduct a substudy which analyses the influence of the project size.

In the study the Markov chain model is used for computing the transition probabilities between the different data science steps. Therefore, they assume that only the current state influences the prediction of the next step.

The following categories are used in this study: helper functions, load data, data pre-processing, data exploration, modelling, evaluation, prediction, result visualization, save results and comment only. These are quite broad categories, making them smaller could lead to more insight on the workflow.

Furthermore, they could have used multiple annotators and/or especially always the same annotators on every notebook to make sure that there is a continuous and non-biased labelling.

Even though it was easy to replicate the results for all important stats in the paper, it would have been helpful if they provided also insights for all feature sets within the code. This would have made it possible to replicate all results, especially those from the multi and single label classification. As there is no clear breakdown, we can only assume that our results are correct and that there are deviations.

Algorithm	Accuracy (Paper)	Accuracy (Our Results)
Random Forest	0.624	0.700
Decision Tree	0.505	0.586
Gradient Boosting	0.620	0.689
Logistic Support Vector Machine	0.640	0.652
Support Vector Machine	0.633	0.639
Logistic Regression	0.627	0.638

Table 3: Comparison of Results for Single Label Classification for feature set `code-comment`

Appendix A

Appendix B

problems	encountered
A. Code/Setup Difficulties	
1. Code not provided	no
2. Code partially not provided	yes
3. Faulty code provided	yes
4. Information about software versions missing	no
5. Specific hardware and software setup necessary	no
B. Data	
1. Data not provided	no
2. Data partially not provided	no
3. Metadata not provided	no
C. Process	
1. Comparison metrics or baselines not discussed	no
2. Experimental setup not described	no
3. Experiment workflow incomplete	yes
4. Inconsistencies in paper, code and data	no
5. Results differ significantly	no

Table 4: Possible and encountered difficulties